

Static and Dynamic Tests on a 40-nm Commercial SRAM under Muons and Neutrons

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Abstract

The single-bit and multiple-cell upset cross sections for positive and negative muons and 14-MeV neutrons of a commercial 40-nm CMOS SRAM have been experimentally determined in static and dynamic modes. In the case of the muons, the momentum with the highest cross section was predicted by EVA, a custom simulation tool, in spite of not having the characteristics of the chemicals used to build the device and the printed circuit boards. Positive muons only cause single-bit upsets, while negative muons and neutrons also induce multiple cell upsets of various multiplicities. The number of multiple events was determined by using LELAPE, a tool that explores the statistical properties of the set of data. In all the tests, the static cross-section was on the same order as the dynamic one, or even higher. Besides, in the case of muons, the cross section is not negligible at standard power supply voltages. These phenomena are attributed to a side effect of the internal circuitry added by the manufacturer to adapt the bias voltage and to minimize the power consumption.

Index Terms

Muons, Multiple Cell Upset (MCU), neutrons, Single Bit Upset (SBU), Single Event Effect (SEE), Single Event Upset (SEU), Static Random Access Memory (SRAM).

I. INTRODUCTION

COSMIC rays at sea level are mainly composed of muons and neutrons. The effects of neutrons on commercial memories have been thoroughly studied, but little is known about muon effects, even though these particles are expected to affect devices built with technologies below 28 nm [1]. This paper investigates the cross-sections of both positive and negative muons, and of 14-MeV neutrons, examining the effects of power supply voltage and operation mode (static or dynamic).

Radiation-induced muon effects on microelectronic devices have been known since long ago [2]. Thus, radiation ground tests have shown that NAND flash memories [3] and bulk Static Random Access Memories (SRAMs) [4], [5] are sensitive to positive muons (μ^+). Technology miniaturization [4], [6], bias voltage [5], and angle of incidence [7] are additional key aspects that explain the increased sensitivity to Single Event Effects (SEE) in modern electronic devices exposed to natural radiation.

Negative muons (μ^-) have also been shown to be significant contributors to the total SEE Soft Error Rate (SER). Recent radiation experiments have proved that SEE cross sections for μ^- are significantly higher than those for μ^+ [8], [9]. The reasons are the capture reactions for μ^- (which are absent for μ^+) that produce secondary ions with a higher Linear Energy Transfer (LET) than the muon itself [8]. These mechanisms are further studied in other works [10]–[14] and also explain that the sensitivity of devices to multiple events, such as multiple-cell upsets (MCUs) or multiple-bit upsets (MBUs), opposed to single bit upsets (SBUs), is significantly higher for μ^- than for μ^+ . Let us remember that an SBU is just an isolated bitflip, whereas an MCU is a cluster of adjacent flipped cells originating in a unique particle impact, which is called MBU if the cells are in the same word. All these phenomena fall in the broader family of Single Event Upsets (SEU). Fin FET [15], Silicon On Thin BOX (SOTB) [12], and Ultra-Thin Body and Buried Oxide Silicon On Insulator (UTTB-SOI) [16] SRAMs have also been examined to μ^+ and μ^- , showing considerably lower SEE sensitivities than bulk CMOS technologies.

A review of the literature reveals that most of the works studying the muon-induced SEEs focus on custom devices manufactured by the researchers themselves. Little attention has been paid to commercial devices, and this paper aims to demonstrate that this technique can be used with Commercial-Off-The-Shelf (COTS) memories. Besides, to the authors' knowledge, there is no work in which the SRAMs were tested in dynamic mode. It is well known that this factor strongly affects the tolerance to radiation. For example, Tsiligliannis et al. discovered that a 90-nm memory exposed to 14-MeV neutrons only showed SEUs in static mode, but Single-Event Functional Interruptions (SEFI) and microlatchups in dynamic mode [17]. This paper aims to clarify whether this is an important factor in the study of memories under muons.

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The COTS 40-nm memory used in the experiments presented in this paper has been used by many authors to understand the SEEs in this technology [18]–[27]. However, the analysis of the data from tests on this memory presents an important problem. The internal organization of the memory is unknown since the manufacturer does not provide access to proprietary information, so it was only possible to provide cross sections for the total number of bits, but not for the multiplicity of the events. This paper proposes a solution to this problem and can extract more accurate information in spite of the internal structure being unknown.

All these experimental results will help to improve calculations of soft error rates in this family of memories in typical environments, either in static or dynamic mode. Simulation-based techniques have also been proposed to estimate the effects of muons on electronics. Thus, Monte Carlo simulators MUSCA-SEP3 [28] and FLUKA [29] have been used to estimate the muon radial ionization profile in the SEU sensitivity for nanoscale technologies (65-nm down to 14-nm), as well as the terrestrial and atmospheric muon flux at various altitudes above sea level [30]. Some methods have also been proposed to estimate the SEE muon-induced cross-section of SRAMs using data issued from experiments with low-energy protons [31], alpha particles [32] or heavy-ions [33].

II. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Electronic setup

The device selected for the test was the IS61WV204816BLL-10TLI by ISSI, a 32-Mbit 40-nm bulk CMOS SRAM, already studied by several authors as a test vehicle for this technology node [20], [27]. Unfortunately, there is no public information about the internal structure, so these authors have provided only data about the SEU cross-section, not separating the set of bitflips in events of different multiplicities.

The sample, in the 48-pin TSOP-I package, was placed on a small board that could be plugged into an expansion card for a NUCLEO-L552ZE-Q, an STM32 Nucleo-144 development kit. The microcontroller inside this board could write and read the memory, control the power supply voltage for the SRAM and the level shifters with 1-mV accuracy by means of a 12-bit Digital-to-Analog Converter and a Class-A output stage, which consisted in a pass NPN bipolar junction transistor and a dual bipolar op amp, measure the temperature and the quiescent current, thus triggering the protection against latch-up if necessary, and establish the communication with a laptop through the USB port. Given the characteristics of the controlled power supply, it was not possible to reach the standard 3.3-V output voltage, so a slightly lower value, around 3.2 V, was used instead. The firmware of the microcontroller was developed in Mbed Community Edition with the ARM GNU toolchain for 32-bit devices (v14.3.2). The USB cable connection was modified to attach a dead-man warning system, consisting of a Raspberry Pi Pico and mechanical relays. In the case of that the Raspberry Pi does not receive any message from the microcontroller in a set time (120 s), it disconnects the +5 V power supply, resets the systems and warns the researchers to restart the test.

To perform the static tests, the system could write or read the full content of the memory in less than 5 s and steadily change the power supply voltage to the required value. The SRAM power supply voltage changed as follows: just after the microcontroller got the command to increase or decrease the voltage, it measures the value at the moment and sends the new values to the DAC in such a way that, starting from the initial value, it changes in steps of 1 mV every 2 ms. The presence of bypass capacitors made for a smooth transition. Before the irradiation, it was verified that the system was stable for longer than 12 h at the lowest bias voltage. The microcontroller was programmed to perform five different dynamic tests (Table I) [34]. There was a significant difference in the duration of the dynamic tests. For instance, a round lasted for 7 s in the dynamic classic test, but 520 s in mMATS+, 1050 s in March C-, 2349 s in Dynamic Stress. The bottleneck was the switching of the microcontroller bidirectional ports from input to output states and vice versa. In these tests, a word is read and written every 125 μ s, so it is quite difficult to capture single event transients. However, they can activate the state of peripheral and power blocks, thus favoring the occurrence of other phenomena such as SEFIs, microlatchups, etc. Dynamic tests underestimate the number of events since they do not detect bitflips occurring in the last step of the cycle if the word was affected after being read by the microcontroller. This is not important in most tests if they are long enough, but it is a serious concern in the dynamic classic test. It only detects 50% of the bitflips originating in SEUs, so the apparent measured cross sections must be multiplied by 2. Hereinafter, the reported cross sections for these tests are corrected by this factor.

It is essential to mention that the SRAM was placed on the backside of the small board (Fig. 1). Thus, incident particles must cross the plastic package and a 1.6-mm FR4 epoxy layer with four 35- μ m copper layers, containing ground and power planes and tracks. This idea was taken from the interesting experiments performed at the J-PARC muon facility in Japan [7], [16], [35], in which the epoxy layer was used to stop the muons in such a way that the Bragg peak (\sim 8 keV) is reached near the sensitive area of the device.

B. Irradiation Facilities

The muon experiments were carried out at the RIKEN-RAL Port4 muon beamline of the ISIS Neutron and Muon Source of the STFC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory using the MEIS setup [36]. This facility provides a beam of positive or negative muons with tunable momentum [37] and has been used in the past to understand the effects of muons on memories [5]. The positive muon experiments were performed in December 2024, and those with negative muons in September 2025.

TABLE I
PROCEDURE TO PERFORM DIFFERENT DYNAMIC TESTS

Name	Test
March C-	(w0); (r0,w1); (r1,w0); (r0,w1); (r1,w0); (r0)
Mats+	(w0); (r0w1); (r1w0)
mMats+	(r0w1); (r1w0)
Dynamic Stress	(r1,w0,r0,r0,r0,r0)
	(r0,w1,r1,r1,r1,r1)
	(r1,w0,r0,r0,r0,r0)
	(r0,w1,r1,r1,r1,r1)
	(r1,w0,r0,r0,r0,r0)
Dynamic Classic	(r0,w1,r1,r1,r1,r1)
	(w0); (r0); (w1); (r1)

Fig. 1. Test setup for the muon irradiation tests. One can see the Nucleo-144, the expansion board, and the small board with the memory near the beam exit. The backside of the small board is also shown in the bottom-right corner of the picture.

The neutron tests were performed in February 2025 at the Frascati Neutron Generator (FNG), a 14-MeV neutron source installed and operating at the ENEA Frascati Research Centre (Italy). It relies on the typical D-T fusion nuclear reactions and can provide a maximum neutron flux of up to $5 \cdot 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ on a typical sample in front of the source [38]. However, in the experiments the flux was reduced to around $10^7 \text{ cm}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. The beam section, aligned with the chip center, was circular with a 1-cm diameter, and the neutrons fell upon the device following the normal direction. The fluence uncertainty is estimated to be not higher than $\pm 3 \%$.

Fig. 2. Layers of different materials that the particles must cross before reaching the sensitive zone. Lower layers model a typical 4-layer 1.6-mm FR4 board, and the upper a 350- μm Silicon dice wrapped in molded epoxy plastic reaching a total 1.2-mm height.

III. RESULTS

The same sample and writing/reading system were used in all the experimental rounds. Error margins were calculated using the procedure recommended by the European Space Agency [39]. All experimental data including the identification of upset cells in each experiment, the number of events, the duration of the tests, and other related details as well as the data processing files, are freely available for review and reuse in other works at <https://zenodo.org/records/17500462>.

A. Positive Muons

The first step consisted in finding out the momentum with the highest cross-section. The device and the sample holder were modeled as shown in Fig. 2, and this structure was simulated in EVA [40], [41], a software that works as an interface for SRIM 2013 [42], [43], thus helping to know how muons interact with matter. In spite of the fact that SRIM does not include muons in its list of possible ions, the interaction of muons and protons are both dominated by electronic stopping power, so muons are equivalent to protons with the same energy but with $m_\mu/m_p \simeq 1/9$ [44], [45]. According to this tool, 39 MeV/c muons, both positive and negative, are the most effective to induce single events since the absorption peak is near the upper interface Si-Plastic (Fig. 3). However, as there are some unknown parameters (epoxy composition, silicon depth, etc.), this value must be considered just a starting point to find the actual peak position.

The memory was filled with the 0x5555 pattern, and the power supply voltage was reduced to 710 mV, the lowest experimental value that allowed the tested sample to retain the information for longer than 12 h, and measured before the irradiation campaigns. This value was defined as the 5 mV above the voltage at which the very first cell failed, even though most of the

Fig. 3. Stopped muons per μm vs. penetration depth for different momenta according to EVA. Every curve was obtained by calculating the trajectory of 100,000 particles. As one can see, the curve for 39 MeV/c is the one for which more muons are stopped in the sensitive zone. In the silicon sensitive zone, around 325 muons out of 100,000 are stopped per μm .

cells still worked even at 650 mV. The device was irradiated in static mode, and the affected addresses were recorded for later analysis. The duration of the static tests ranged from 10 to 60 minutes, depending on the state of the beam and the need to improve the measurements in the interesting cases. Fig. 4 shows that the experimental peak was close to the predicted value, around 42 MeV/c.

In spite of the large uncertainty of the measured cross sections, this momentum was chosen for the rest of the experiment. Next, the dependence of the cross-section on the power supply voltage was studied, changing this parameter from 710 mV to 2.6 V, the lowest nominal voltage value according to the manufacturer (Fig. 5). Two interesting conclusions can be drawn from these results. Initially, the cross-section quickly decreases as the power supply voltage increases, but, instead of the exponential decrease of several orders of magnitude reported in the literature, it reaches a saturation value around 20 times smaller than the highest cross-section. In Section IV-B, it is discussed that rather than a characteristic of 40-nm CMOS technology, this behavior is related to the presence of power structures in COTS devices. Besides, an analysis of the set of results done with the LELAPE tool [46] indicates that the bitflips are compatible with a scenario with only SBUs and that there are no hints of occurrences of MCUs. As mentioned above in the Introduction, one of the main differences between positive and negative muons is that only the latter can induce MCUs [11].

All the dynamic tests in Table I were carried out, in some cases with two power supply values (2.6 V, 3.2 V). Due to time constraints, the more accurate results were obtained for Dynamic Stress, March C-, and Dynamic Classic, marked with a star in Table II. As in the case of static tests, only SBUs occurred during the tests.

Acknowledging that the uncertainty margins are wide due to the collection of a few events, it can be seen that all the measurements are compatible with the expected value of the static SBU cross-section. Therefore, the dynamic mode does not lead to a significant increase of the soft error rate. This is the opposite of what is reported in neutron tests by other works [17], in which micro-latchups and single event functional interrupts (SEFIs) boost the SEU cross-section.

B. Negative Muons

The same procedure as depicted in Section III-A was followed in this round of experiments, performing 10 to 20-min static tests. First of all, all the momentum with the highest cross section was sought and, as predicted by the simulations, it was

Fig. 4. SBU per-bit cross section at 710 mV vs. momentum of positive muons.

TABLE II
SBU PER-BIT CROSS-SECTION IN DYNAMIC TESTS FOR 42-MEV/C POS. MUONS. THE STAR MARKS THE MOST ACCURATE MEASUREMENTS.

Test	SBU Cross Section	
	Voltage: 2.68 V	Voltage: 3.23 V
Dynamic Stress	$2.5^{+1.1}_{-1.5}$ *	$2.4^{+0.6}_{-0.8}$ *
March C-	—	$1.8^{+0.9}_{-1.5}$ *
Dynamic Classic	< 122	$2.4^{+13.8}_{-2.0}$ *
MATS+	$15.8^{+72.4}_{-15.4}$	$16.3^{+74.4}_{-15.9}$
mMATS+	$16.9^{+77.5}_{-16.5}$	< 67.0

$\cdot 10^{-14}$ cm²/bit

Static SBU cross-section at 2.6 V: $2.8^{+7.2}_{-2.4} \cdot 10^{-14}$ cm²/bit.

found at the same position as in tests with positive muons, 42 MeV/c (Fig. 6). This experiment showed that the negative-muon cross section is around three orders of magnitude higher than that of positive ones, as observed by other authors and typically attributed to the muon capture phenomenon [11], [47], [48].

Next, the correlation between the cross-section and power supply voltage for this momentum was measured (Fig. 7), and several differences with the tests with the positive muons were observed. Firstly, all the cross-section values for different voltages are on the same order of magnitude since the highest cross-section value is hardly four times the lowest. This contrasts with the quick decrease observed with positive muons. At any rate, this behavior has been depicted in the literature, and it is worth noting that there is an apparent secondary peak at 2.6 V of unknown origin. Also, the LELAPE tool showed that the sets of bitflips could not be explained if only SBUs occurred. The tool provided several anomalies that allowed linking bitflip addresses to identify MCUs. Let us briefly explain how this tool works. First of all, if the k^{th} cell of the A^{th} word is flipped, with $k \in [0, 15]$ and $A \in [0, 2^{21} - 1]$, the pseudo-address (PA) of the flipped cell is defined as

$$PA = A \cdot 16 + k$$

in binary format. Hence, all the pairs of cells with pseudo-addresses PA_1 and PA_2 such that $xor(PA_1, PA_2) = S$, with S one of the anomalies shown in Table V, are very probably adjacent cells and belonging to the same MCU [46].

Fig. 5. SBU per-bit cross-section per bit for 42-MeV/c positive muons vs. power supply voltage. The dot corresponding to 3.2 V could not be measured due to time constraints.

TABLE III
CROSS SECTIONS FOR 42-MEV NEGATIVE MUONS

Voltage	Multiplicity		
	1	2	3
710	5.24 ^{+1.24} _{-1.06}	1.79 ^{+0.78} _{-0.59}	0.31 ^{+0.41} _{-0.21}
750	3.83 ^{+1.47} _{-1.15}	1.38 ^{+0.98} _{-0.65}	< 0.39
800	2.49 ^{+1.28} _{-0.93}	0.34 ^{+0.65} _{-0.27}	0.23 ^{+0.59} _{-0.20}
900	2.03 ^{+1.07} _{-0.77}	0.19 ^{+2.91} _{-0.17}	0.10 ^{+0.44} _{-0.09}
1200	2.29 ^{+1.81} _{-1.15}	0.42 ^{+1.09} _{-0.37}	< 0.77
2600	4.32 ^{+2.43} _{-1.72}	1.14 ^{+1.52} _{-0.77}	< 0.84
3300	1.63 ^{+0.62} _{-0.49}	0.41 ^{+0.37} _{-0.22}	< 0.17
mV	× 10 ⁻¹¹ cm ² /bit		

However, the neutron tests shown in Section III-C provoked thousands of bitflips and allowed obtaining a very large set of anomalies, so the reconstruction of the MCUs was done with them. Most of the bitflips induced by the negative muons were associated with SBUs or 2-bit MCUs, although an 8-bit MCU was identified in the set of data obtained with 3.2 V and 42 MeV/c. Table III shows the cross sections for different multiplicities from 1 to 3. The anomalous peak at 2.6 V also appears not only for the total number of bitflips but also for events of different multiplicities.

Finally, several dynamic tests were performed. Due to time constraints, the selected tests were Dynamic Classic at 2.6 V and 3.2 V, and March C- at 3.2 V. The latter test lasted for much longer than the former. The cross sections for events of different multiplicities are shown in Table IV, and, as in the case of the positive muons, the values for dynamic tests are compatible with the values measured in static mode, the only exception being the Dynamic Classic value at 2.6 V, the cross sections of which are clearly reduced.

Fig. 6. Cross section for total number of bitflips at 710 mV vs. momentum of negative muons.

TABLE IV
CROSS SECTIONS FOR STATIC AND DYNAMIC TESTS WITH NEGATIVE MUONS.

Test @ 3.2 V	Multiplicity			Total
	1	2	3	
Static	$1.63^{+0.62}_{-0.49}$	$0.41^{+0.37}_{-0.22}$	< 0.17	$2.80^{+0.79}_{-0.65}$
Dyn. Classic	$2.8^{+1.7}_{-1.0}$	$0.12^{+0.58}_{-0.12}$	$0.12^{+0.58}_{-0.12}$	$3.4^{+1.5}_{-0.6}$
March C-	$1.43^{+0.18}_{-0.17}$	$0.28^{+0.09}_{-0.07}$	$0.06^{+0.05}_{-0.03}$	$2.45^{+0.23}_{-0.22}$
Test @ 2.6 V				
Static	$4.32^{+2.43}_{-1.72}$	$1.14^{+1.52}_{-0.77}$	< 0.84	$6.60^{+2.88}_{-2.18}$
Dyn. Classic	$0.88^{+0.84}_{-0.50}$	$0.22^{+0.58}_{-0.20}$	< 0.40	$1.3^{+3.6}_{-0.6}$
$\times 10^{-11} \text{ cm}^2/\text{bit}$				

C. 14-MeV Neutrons

The SRAM was tested at the ENEA Frascati Neutron Generator (FNG) with the same setup as that of the muon tests. Thus, the device was irradiated through the backside of the board, easily crossed by 14-MeV neutrons, although the energy spectrum slightly changed, as Fig. 8 shows. Even though the energy of the neutrons produced by tritium-deuterium fusion reactions is distributed in a narrow peak around 14 MeV, there is a secondary peak around 2.5 MeV due to deuterium-deuterium reactions, and a tail till the lower energies, even thermalized, due to the scattering with the surrounding materials.

This test was included in a large campaign of irradiations investigating different aspects. Given that the flux was much higher than in the case of the muons, static tests cast meaningful results in rounds of 15 to 30 s. As a result of this, it was possible to gather up to 55,593 events in 60 rounds (total fluence of $1.93 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-2}$), powering up the SRAM at 3.2 V and with 0x5555 pattern.

The LELAPE tool detected statistical anomalies, listed in Table V, that allowed grouping some of the bitflips into MCUs. Around 35 anomalies were detected, although not all were equally relevant. Table V also shows the occurrence of each one of these anomalies in 2-bit MCU, showing that just the first two ones (i.e., 0x000080 and 0x000180) represented 2/3 of the total pairs. An interesting fact is that all the anomalies in Table V end in 0. This number is related to the bit position in the

Fig. 7. Total-bitflip cross-section per bit for 42-MeV/c negative muons vs. power supply voltage. Unlike Fig. 5, the Y-axis could be drawn in a linear scale instead of logarithmic since all of the values are on the same order of magnitude.

TABLE V
MOST FREQUENT ANOMALIES FOUND BY LELAPE WHEN ANALYZING THE BITFLIPS FOR THE EXPERIMENT WITH 14-MeV NEUTRONS AND THE PROBABILITY OF OCCURRING IN 2-BIT MCUS.

Anomaly	Occurr.	Anomaly	Occurr.	Anomaly	Occurr.
0x000080	44.4 %	0x004000	3.6 %	0x780180	1.3 %
0x000180	21.5 %	0x380180	2.7 %	0x01C000	0.9 %
0x080180	10.3 %	0x004080	2.2 %	0x00C180	0.6 %
0x180180	6.2 %	0x00C000	2.0 %	0x03C000	0.5 %

cell (k), not to the word address (A), and indicates that the anomalies that were found never involved 2 bitcells in the same word, which is consistent with the usage of bit interleaving in this memory. Besides, it is possible to get from the values of the anomalies and their probabilities clues to understand the scrambling introduced in this memory.

This information made it possible to classify the bitflips into SBUs and MCUs of different sizes. Thus, the original 55,593 bitflips were classified into 35,747 SBUs, 7,275 2-bit MCUs, 1,209 3-bit MCUs, and events of larger sizes up to 23 bits. The derived cross sections are shown in Fig. 9. It is worth mentioning that, using statistical models to predict the occurrence of false MCUs¹, it could be determined that the expected numbers of false 2-bit & 3-bit MCUs were 26.7 & 8.7, two or more orders of magnitude below the observed values and hence negligible.

The total bit-flip cross-section measured in these tests, $8.58 \cdot 10^{-15} \text{ cm}^2/\text{bit} \equiv 2.88 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^2/\text{device}$, is slightly lower than the value reported by Cecchetto *et al.* for the same device at GENEPI2-LPSC 14-MeV neutron source ($3.3 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^2/\text{device}$ in [27]). This can be attributed to several factors. First, variability from sample to sample and the attenuation of the neutrons after crossing the 1.6-mm FR4 layer. However, in at least one of the rounds, the number of bitflips grew to 5,251 bitflips, even though the average number of bitflips per round was 927. Using the criterion set in [50], this round was removed from the analysis since there was probably a SEFI. If this round was included to calculate σ_{SEU} , the new value would be $3.1 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^2/\text{device}$, really close to that reported in [27]. Curiously, both values are around 50% the value reported in [20] for the same device, particle and energy ($1.81 \cdot 10^{-14} \text{ cm}^2$)

The dependence of the 14-MeV neutron cross-sections on the power supply voltage was also investigated (Fig. 10). For the sake of clarity, only the cross sections for SBUs and 2-bit MCUs are included in the graph. One can see that the cross sections are more or less constant for power supply voltages above 1.0 V. Below, the value quickly increases, but, unlike in the case

¹A false MCU is the occurrence of several SBUs at neighbor cells by chance, that can be misled with a true MCU.

Fig. 8. Neutron energy spectrum flux normalized per source neutron as calculated by MCNP5 and FENDL3.1 nuclear data [49]. 86.9 % of the neutrons have an energy value between 13.8 and 15.7 MeV, 9.8 % between 1.0 and 13.8 MeV.

of the positive muons (Fig. 5), the growth is hardly $\times 2.5$, quite similar to the case of negative muons. Similar cross-section values were measured when the device was written with a 0x0000 pattern. Unlike the case of negative muons, no evidence of an anomalous peak at 2.6 V was found.

Finally, due to time constraints, only the Dynamic Classic test at 2.6 and 3.2 V could be performed. This specific test was selected since every round took only 7 seconds, so many were done during the 15-minute irradiation rounds. Events with multiplicities up to 9 were registered, with the different cross sections shown in Table VI. Given that in these rounds only around 1,225 bitflips were recorded with a neutron fluence of $8.2 \cdot 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-2}$, the uncertainty for the dynamic tests is larger than that of the static ones. There is no difference between performing a test with 2.6V or 3.2V, which is more or less the range of nominal operation voltage according to the manufacturer.

IV. DISCUSSION

A major issue with radiation testing on electronic components is the lack of information about the internal structure of the device, beyond general notes such as typical manufacturing length. In consequence, it is hard to correctly interpret the experimental results. The only viable options are to perform some kind of reverse engineering (such as laser tests, or statistical study) or assume that common strategies have been implemented, and it must always be kept in mind that the results are only applicable to that particular model, and may not be valid for other devices from different manufacturers, or even from the same one.

A. Possible implications in other COTS devices

The results shown in the previous section have demonstrated that muons can induce single events in commercial SRAMs even at the nominal voltage value. This raises the possibility of observing muon-induced single events in complex devices such as SRAM-based FPGAs, built with a 40-nm technology node or below. Therefore, it would be interesting to perform in the future muon tests on this family of devices, helped by the EVA tool or equivalent to quickly find the momentum with the highest cross section, and not only neutron tests. Besides, the different cross-section values would help to make good estimations of the SER in natural environments at ground level originating in cosmic rays, such as the data provided in this paper would for this family of SRAMs.

Fig. 9. SBU & MCU cross-section per bit for 14-MeV neutrons at nominal voltage. Cross sections for multiplicities between 1 and 9 are explicitly shown in Table VI. A dashed line sets an upper bound for the cross-section of events of a multiplicity not observed during the tests. σ_{SEU} is calculated by dividing the total number of bitflips independently of their origin by the total fluence.

TABLE VI
CROSS SECTION FOR EVENTS OF DIFFERENT MULTIPLICITY IN DYNAMIC AND STATIC TESTS WITH 14-MeV NEUTRONS. STATIC CROSS-SECTIONS ARE SHOWN AS REFERENCES.

Multip.	Dynamic Classic		Static (0x5555)		
	3.23 V	2.69 V	3.23 V	2.61 V	
1	$5.8^{+0.4}_{-0.4}$	$5.8^{+0.4}_{-0.4}$	5.52 ± 0.06	$6.0^{+1.0}_{-0.9}$	$\times 10^{-15}$
2	$1.16^{+0.18}_{-0.16}$	$1.22^{+0.20}_{-0.18}$	1.11 ± 0.03	$1.2^{+0.5}_{-0.4}$	cm ² /bit
3	$16.6^{+8.0}_{-5.8}$	$11.0^{+7.0}_{-4.8}$	18.7 ± 1.0	$22.3^{+26.2}_{-14.1}$	
4	$3.4^{+4.4}_{-2.2}$	$5.8^{+0.4}_{-0.4}$	4.4 ± 0.5	$7.4^{+19.4}_{-6.5}$	
5	$1.4^{+3.4}_{-1.2}$	$0.7^{+3.3}_{-0.7}$	$1.1^{+0.3}_{-0.2}$	< 13.7	
6	$0.66^{+3.04}_{-0.64}$	< 2.6	$0.52^{+0.21}_{-0.16}$	< 13.7	$\times 10^{-17}$
7	< 2.4	< 2.6	$0.11^{+0.11}_{-0.06}$	< 13.7	cm ² /bit
8	< 2.4	< 2.6	$0.19^{+0.14}_{-0.09}$	< 13.7	
9	$0.66^{+3.04}_{-0.64}$	< 2.6	$0.06^{+0.10}_{-0.04}$	< 13.7	
Total bit-flips	9.94 ± 0.46	9.94 ± 0.50	8.58 ± 0.07	9.5 ± 1.2	$\times 10^{-15}$ cm ² /bit

B. Interpretation of Static Tests

Let us now interpret the experimental data collected from the various test campaigns. The static neutron tests yield results that align well with those observed in commercial SRAMs: the cross section decreases as the power supply voltage is reduced, with lower cross section values for the largest multiplicities. Muon tests are more interesting, since the COTS device used for the tests is much more complex than custom devices used in previous works. For instance, similarities can be observed between the tests performed on both types of memory, but also some striking differences. Like in other works [8], [11], [15]:

- Positive muons only induce SBUs, and not MCUs. The cross section quickly falls with the power supply value.
- Negative muons induce a large amount of multiple cell upsets. The cross sections are quite independent of the power supply voltage.
- Negative muons have larger cross sections than positive muons

Fig. 10. Evolution of the cross-section for SBUs and 2-bit MCUs for 14-MeV neutrons with several power supply voltage values.

- The momenta for the highest cross sections are quite close, if not identical.

The different behavior of the SRAM in positive and negative muon tests has been attributed to two phenomena: first of all, the negative muon capture releases particles that increase the cross sections and produce MCUs. Besides, the stabilization of the cross-section value for large bias voltages has been attributed to the Parasitic Bipolar Amplification (PBA) effect [11], which compensates for the increase in the threshold deposited charge needed to trigger the single event [51].

Nevertheless, some differences are evident:

- The SBU cross section for positive muons at nominal voltages (2.6 V) is hardly 5% of the maximum value measured at 710 mV. In other works that deals with SRAMs in different technology nodes [5], [16], [47], [52], the cross sections falls two or more orders of magnitude with an increase of around 600 mV.
- The values of voltages in our experiments are considerably higher than those shown in other works, where the bias voltage is usually on the order of some tenths of volts, never larger than 1.2 V.

Unfortunately, when the effect of bias voltage in positive-muon irradiations is studied, researchers usually stop at values around 1.0-1.2 V and do not go beyond, probably to avoid damage in the sample, so we do not know if the positive-muon cross section keeps the exponential-like decrease or it reaches a saturation value for high bias voltages.

However, we should not forget that there is key difference between the samples used in other works and the one shown in this manuscript. Thus, whereas in those works a custom SRAM was specifically built for the tests, here the sample is a COTS device that incorporated additional features. COTS CMOS logic devices are designed to be compatible with typical output voltage levels, and power supplies are standardized. The memory used in these tests works with +3.3-V power supplies, but this value is much higher than what is usually applied to the 40-nm CMOS logic devices, with bias voltages not going beyond 1.0-1.2 V. Besides, these memories usually include additional parts to minimize power consumption.

To deal with the first issue, the manufacturers distinguish between the peripheral power supply and the core power supply [53]. The former is the one measured in this manuscript, the latter the one used in other works. Manufacturers add internal blocks to get the appropriate core bias voltage, which mainly consist in voltage references, voltage-down converters, drive MOS transistors, etc. [53]–[57]. For the sake of simplicity, let us symbolize all these elements as a linear voltage regulator (Fig. 11) with the following output function [58]:

$$V_{CC} = \begin{cases} V_L - V_{DO} & V_L < V_{MIN} \\ V_{NOM} \cdot (1 + \alpha \cdot (V_L - V_{MIN})) & V_L > V_{MIN} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

V_{NOM} being the nominal output voltage, V_{DO} the drop-out voltage, $V_{MIN} = V_{NOM} + V_{DO}$, and α the line regulation coefficient. It is postulated that, for this device, V_{CC} is around 1.0-1.2 V. The presence of these structures would explain the

Fig. 11. Linear voltage regulator for commercial advanced CMOS memories. This device provides a bias voltage, V_{BIAS} , on the order of some tenths of volt from the standard power supply, V_L . If this parameter is higher than $V_{BIAS} + V_{DO}$, the output voltage is constant. If V_L falls below this value, the regulator output is around $V_L - V_{DO}$. V_{DO} is the *drop-out* of the regulator.

differences listed above. First of all, due to the drop-out voltage, the minimum SRAM power supply value is higher than the typical values reported in custom devices.

The early saturation in the cross section would be also the result of the shape of Eq. 1. For low voltages, on the order of 1 V or below, the bias voltage has not reached its nominal value and follows the power supply value with a small offset, and graphs do not differ much from those reported in the literature. However, when the nominal voltage is crossed, the output voltage hardly changes, only increasing due to the effect of the line regulation coefficient. Hence, the parts of Figs. 5, 7, and 10 corresponding to power supply voltages between V_{MIN} and 3.3 V only reflects a small range of the cell bias voltage, expanded by the effect of the line regulation effect. This explains the saturation value for the cross section in all the graphs, but also the slight variations around this value, such as the secondary maximum observed around 2.6 V.

At any rate, this is just a hypothesis to explain the observed behavior based on common practices used by the manufacturers. Everything should be confirmed by using nanoprobe or layout analysis, but unfortunately these tools are not currently available for the authors.

C. Interpretation of Dynamic Tests

Experimental results have shown that working in dynamic mode hardly changes the behavior under radiation, at least up to 14-MeV neutrons. There is no evidence of a significant increase or decrease in the cross section for dynamic tests with respect to static ones, as the different tables in this manuscript show. This brings some interesting issues for the development of actual electronic systems to work under radiation. For example, the device studied in this has been proposed as a radiation monitor in some environments [24]–[26]. The fact that the device has similar cross sections for static and dynamic modes allows designing simpler electronic systems, since no continuous writing/reading is necessary.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The SEE sensitivity of a COTS 40-nm SRAM against positive and negative muons and 14-MeV neutrons was studied. In the first case, only SBUs were observed, but they occurred even at nominal voltage. Besides, there is no evidence of an increase in sensitivity in dynamic mode with respect to static mode, as pointed out in other works in the literature under protons or neutrons. In the case of negative muons and neutrons, it was possible to classify bitflips into events with multiplicities up to 8 bits in the former and 23 bits in the latter. An increase in the cross-section was observed at low voltage, but it was not significant. This phenomenon is attributed to the use of internal voltage regulators to adapt typical logic voltage values to the low voltages used to bias the 40-nm memory core. Also, there is not any significant differences among the cross-section values for static and dynamic modes, contrarily to what was expected after checking other relevant related works in the literature.

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REFERENCES

- [1] G. Hubert, D. Regis, A. Cheminet, M. Gatti, and V. Lacoste, "Multi-physics modelling contributions to investigate the atmospheric cosmic rays on the single event upset sensitivity along the scaling trend of CMOS technologies," *Radiat. Prot. Dosim.*, vol. 161, no. 1-4, pp. 290–294, Feb. 2014. doi: 10.1093/rpd/ncu003.
- [2] J. F. Dicello, C. W. McCabe, J. D. Doss, and M. Paciotti, "The Relative Efficiency of Soft-Error Induction in 4K Static RAMS by Muons and Pions," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 30, no. 6, pp. 4613–4615, Dec. 1983. doi: 10.1109/TNS.1983.4333182.
- [3] M. Bagatin *et al.*, "Muon-induced soft errors in 16-nm NAND flash memories," in *IEEE International Reliability Physics Symposium (IRPS)*, (Pasadena, CA, USA), pp. 319–323, Apr. 2016. doi: 10.1109/IRPS.2016.7574552.
- [4] B. D. Sierawski *et al.*, "Muon-induced single event upsets in deep-submicron technology," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 57, no. 6, pp. 3273–3278, Dec. 2010. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2010.2080689.

- [5] B. D. Sierawski *et al.*, "Bias dependence of muon-induced single event upsets in 28 nm static random access memories," in *IEEE International Reliability Physics Symposium*, vol. 1, (Waikoloa, Hawaii, USA), pp. 32–36, June 2014. doi: 10.1109/IRPS.2014.6860585.
- [6] W. Liao *et al.*, "Negative and Positive Muon-Induced SEU Cross Sections in 28-nm and 65-nm Planar Bulk CMOS SRAMs," in *IEEE International Reliability Physics Symposium (IRPS)*, vol. 1, (Monterey, California, USA), pp. 396–400, Mar. 2019. doi: 10.1109/IRPS.2019.8720568.
- [7] Y. Deng *et al.*, "Impact of Irradiation Side on Muon-Induced Single-Event Upsets in 65-nm Bulk SRAMs," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 71, no. 4, pp. 912–920, Apr. 2024. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2024.3378216.
- [8] T. Kato *et al.*, "Muon-induced single-event upsets in 20-nm srams: Comparative characterization with neutrons and alpha particles," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 68, no. 7, pp. 1436–1444, July 2021. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2021.3082559.
- [9] Y. Gomi *et al.*, "Muon-Induced SEU Cross Sections of 12-nm FinFET and 28-nm Planar SRAMs," in *23rd European Conference on Radiation and Its Effects on Components and Systems (RADECS)*, (Toulouse, France), pp. 27–30, Sept. 2023. doi: 10.1109/RADECS59069.2023.10767043.
- [10] A. Akkerman, J. Barak, and N. M. Yitzhak, "Role of elastic scattering of protons, muons, and electrons in inducing single-event upsets," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 64, no. 10, pp. 2648–2660, Oct. 2017. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2017.2747658.
- [11] W. Liao *et al.*, "Measurement and Mechanism Investigation of Negative and Positive Muon-Induced Upsets in 65-nm Bulk SRAMs," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 65, no. 8, pp. 1734–1741, Aug. 2018. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2018.2825469.
- [12] M. Hashimoto, W. Liao, S. Manabe, and Y. Watanabe, "Characterizing soft error rates of 65-nm SOTB and bulk SRAMs with muon and neutron beams," in *IEEE SOI-3D-Subthreshold Microelectronics Technology Unified Conference (S3S)*, (Burlingame, CA, USA), pp. 70–71, Oct. 2018. doi: 10.1109/S3S.2018.8640144.
- [13] W. Liao *et al.*, "Similarity Analysis on Neutron- and Negative Muon-Induced MCUs in 65-nm Bulk SRAM," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 66, no. 7, pp. 1390–1397, July 2019. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2019.2921365.
- [14] M. Hashimoto and W. Liao, "Soft Error and Its Countermeasures in Terrestrial Environment," in *25th Asia and South Pacific Design Automation Conference (ASP-DAC)*, (Beijing, China), pp. 617–622, Jan. 2020. doi: 10.1109/ASP-DAC47756.2020.9045161.
- [15] Y. Gomi *et al.*, "Muon-Induced SEU Analysis and Simulation for Different Cell Types in 12-nm FinFET SRAMs, and 28-nm Planar SRAMs and Register Files," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 72, no. 8, pp. 2751 – 2762, 2025. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2025.3542468.
- [16] S. Manabe *et al.*, "Estimation of Muon-Induced SEU Rates for 65-nm Bulk and UTBB-SOI SRAMs," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 66, no. 7, pp. 1398–1403, July 2019. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2019.2916191.
- [17] G. Tsiligianis *et al.*, "Dynamic Test Methods for COTS SRAMs," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 61, no. 6, pp. 3095–3102, Dec. 2014. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2014.2363123.
- [18] A. Coronetti *et al.*, "Assessment of Proton Direct Ionization for the Radiation Hardness Assurance of Deep Submicron SRAMs Used in Space Applications," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 68, no. 5, pp. 937–948, May 2021. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2021.3061209.
- [19] J. Li, W. Chen, R. Li, G. Wang, and S. Yang, "Study on Transient Ionizing Radiation Effect of 40nm SRAM," in *3rd International Conference on Radiation Effects of Electronic Devices (ICREED)*, (Chongqing, China), pp. 26–29, May 2019. doi: 10.1109/ICREED49760.2019.9205175.
- [20] J. Li *et al.*, "SEU effects induced by Reactor Spallation and Accelerator neutron sources in Nano-SRAMs," in *4th International Conference on Radiation Effects of Electronic Devices (ICREED)*, (Xi'an, China), pp. 51–55, May 2021. doi: 10.1109/ICREED52909.2021.9588670.
- [21] A. Coronetti *et al.*, "Thermal-to-high-energy neutron SEU characterization of commercial SRAMs," in *IEEE Radiation Effects Data Workshop (REDW)*, (Virtual Conference), pp. 32–36, July 2021. doi: 10.1109/NSREC45046.2021.9679344.
- [22] M. Glorieux *et al.*, "Methods for Proton Direct Ionization SEU Characterization and Orbital Error-Rate Estimation," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 71, no. 8, pp. 1707–1714, Aug. 2024. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2024.3396220.
- [23] A. Coronetti, N. Emriskova, R. G. Alía, J. A. V. Sanchez, and A. Mazal, "Assessment of the Quirónsalud Proton Therapy Centre Accelerator for Single Event Effects Testing," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 71, no. 8, pp. 1571–1579, Aug. 2024. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2024.3350202.
- [24] S. Peracchi *et al.*, "LET Calibration of Ion Microbeams and Their SEE Cross Section Characterization," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 71, no. 8, pp. 1565–1570, Aug. 2024. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2024.3372135.
- [25] L. Gabrisch *et al.*, "Quantification of Neutron-Induced Single-Event Upsets in a Static Random-Access Memory by Clinical High-Energy Photon Beam," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 71, no. 8, pp. 1503–1510, Aug. 2024. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2024.3427773.
- [26] M. Sacristán-Barbero *et al.*, "Characterization of Fragmented Ultrahigh-Energy Heavy Ion Beam and Its Effects on Electronics Single-Event Effect Testing," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 71, no. 8, pp. 1557–1564, Aug. 2024. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2024.3396737.
- [27] M. Cecchetto *et al.*, "Energy Deposition and Characterization of Single Event Upset and Latch-up Cross Sections with 14 MeV and Thermal Neutrons," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, pp. 2847 – 2856, Aug. 2025. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2025.3548299.
- [28] P. L. Cavoli, G. Hubert, and J. Busto, "Study of atmospheric muon interactions in Si nanoscale devices," *J. Instrum.*, vol. 12, no. 12, p. P12021, Dec. 2017. doi: 10.1088/1748-0221/12/12/P12021.
- [29] A. Infantino, R. G. Alía, and M. Brugger, "Monte Carlo Evaluation of Single Event Effects in a Deep-Submicron Bulk Technology: Comparison Between Atmospheric and Accelerator Environment," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 64, no. 1, pp. 596–604, Jan. 2017. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2016.2621238.
- [30] A. Infantino *et al.*, "FLUKA Monte Carlo assessment of the terrestrial muon flux at low energies and comparison against experimental measurements," *Nucl. Instrum. Methods Phys. Res., Sect. A*, vol. 838, pp. 109–116, 2016. doi: 10.1016/j.nima.2016.09.012.
- [31] J. M. Trippe *et al.*, "Predicting the vulnerability of memories to muon-induced SEUs with low-energy proton tests informed by Monte Carlo simulations," in *IEEE International Reliability Physics Symposium (IRPS)*, (Pasadena, CA, USA), pp. 789–794, Apr. 2016. doi: 10.1109/IRPS.2016.7574642.
- [32] Y.-P. Fang and A. S. Oates, "Muon-induced soft errors in sram circuits in the terrestrial environment," *IEEE Trans. Device Mater. Reliab.*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 115–122, Mar. 2015. doi: 10.1109/TDMR.2015.2396673.
- [33] J. M. Trippe *et al.*, "Predicting Muon-Induced SEU Rates for a 28-nm SRAM Using Protons and Heavy Ions to Calibrate the Sensitive Volume Model," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 65, no. 2, pp. 712–718, Feb. 2018.
- [34] L. Dilillo *et al.*, "Soft errors in commercial off-the-shelf static random access memories," *Semicond. Sci. Tech.*, vol. 32, no 1, Dec. 2016. Article Number 013006. doi: 10.1088/1361-6641/32/1/013006.
- [35] W. Liao *et al.*, "Impact of the Angle of Incidence on Negative Muon-Induced SEU Cross Sections of 65-nm Bulk and FDSOI SRAMs," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 67, no. 7, pp. 1566–1572, July 2020. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2020.2976125.
- [36] A. Hillier *et al.*, "Pulsed muons at ISIS - 40 years and counting," in *16th Internat. Confer. on Muon Spin Rotation, Relaxation and Resonance (muSR2025)*, (St. Johns, Newfoundland, Canada), July 2025. In press.
- [37] A. D. Hillier, J. S. Lord, K. Ishida, and C. Rogers, "Muons at ISIS," *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. Math. Phys. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 377, Dec. 2018. Article number 20180064. doi: 10.1098/rsta.2018.0064.
- [38] M. Martone, M. Angelone, and M. Pillon, "The 14 MeV Frascati neutron generator," *J. Nucl. Mater.*, vol. 212215, Part. B, pp. 1661–1664, Sept. 1994. doi: 10.1016/0022-3115(94)91109-6.
- [39] European Space Agency, "Single Event Effects Test Method and Guidelines. ESCC Basic Specification No. 2510. Issue 2," Oct. 2014. Online. Available on <https://escies.org/escs-specs/published/25100.pdf>.
- [40] M. Bjorklund *et al.*, "EVA: A User-Friendly Analysis Package for Negative Muon Elemental Analysis," in *16th Internat. Confer. on Muon Spin Rotation, Relaxation and Resonance (muSR2025)*, (St. Johns, Newfoundland, Canada), July 2025. In press.
- [41] "EVA - Elemental Visual Analysis," 2025. Online. Available on <https://github.com/ISISMuon/EVA>.
- [42] J. F. Ziegler, M. Ziegler, and J. Biersack, "SRIM The stopping and range of ions in matter (2010)," *Nucl. Instrum. Methods Phys. Res. Sect. B Beam Interact. Mater. At.*, vol. 268, no. 11, pp. 1818–1823, 2010. doi: 10.1016/j.nimb.2010.02.091.
- [43] J. F. Ziegler, "SRIM The Stopping and Range of Ions in Matter.," 2013. Online. Available on <http://srim.org/>.

- [44] E. Morenzoni *et al.*, "Implantation studies of kev positive muons in thin metallic layers," *Nucl. Instrum. Methods Phys. Res. Sect. B Beam Interact. Mater. At.*, vol. 192, no. 3, pp. 254–266, May 2002. doi: 10.1016/s0168-583x(01)01166-1.
- [45] S. J. Blundell *et al.*, eds., *Muon Spectroscopy: An Introduction*, ch. 17, pp. 263–273. Oxford University Press, Nov. 2021. doi: 10.1093/oso/9780198858959.003.0017.
- [46] J. A. Clemente, M. Rezaei, J. C. Fabero, H. Mecha, and F. J. Franco, "LELAPE: An Open-Source Tool to Classify SEUs According to Their Multiplicity in Radiation-Ground Tests on Memories," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 71, no. 10, pp. 2260–2271, Oct. 2024. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2024.3450607.
- [47] S. Manabe *et al.*, "Negative and Positive Muon-Induced Single Event Upsets in 65-nm UTBB SOI SRAMs," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 65, no. 8, pp. 1742–1749, Aug. 2018. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2018.2839704.
- [48] J.-L. Autran and D. Munteanu, "Interactions of Low-Energy Muons with Silicon: Numerical Simulation of Negative Muon Capture and Prospects for Soft Errors," *J. Nucl. Eng.*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 91–110, Mar. 2024. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/jne5010007>.
- [49] MCNPX-5 Monte Carlo Team, MCNP, "A General Monte Carlo N-particle transport code overview and theory (Version 5, vol. I)," 2003. Los Alamos National Laboratory, Report LA-UR-03-1987, 2003, 24 April (Revised 3.10.05). Online.
- [50] A. Pérez-Celis, C. Thurlow, and M. Wirthlin, "Identifying Radiation-Induced Micro-SEFs in SRAM FPGAs," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 68, no. 10, pp. 2480–2487, Oct. 2021. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2021.3108572.
- [51] K. Osada, K. Yamaguchi, Y. Saitoh, and T. Kawahara, "SRAM immunity to cosmic-ray-induced multierrors based on analysis of an induced parasitic bipolar effect," *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 39, no. 5, pp. 827–833, May 2004. doi: 10.1109/JSSC.2004.826321.
- [52] T. Mahara *et al.*, "Irradiation Test of 65-nm Bulk SRAMs With DC Muon Beam at RCNP-MuSIC Facility," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 67, no. 7, pp. 1555–1559, July 2020. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2020.2972022.
- [53] F.-S. Lai and C.-F. Lee, "On-Chip Voltage Down Converter to Improve SRAM Read/Write Margin and Static Power for Sub-Nano CMOS Technology," *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 42, no. 9, pp. 2061–2070, Sept. 2007. doi: 10.1109/JSSC.2007.903072.
- [54] C. Lee, W. Lin, F. Lai, and S. Lin, "On-Chip VDC Circuit for SRAM Power Management," in *International Symposium on VLSI Design, Automation and Test (VLSI-DAT)*, (Hsinchu, Taiwan), pp. 105–108, Apr. 2007. doi: 10.1109/VDAT.2007.372757.
- [55] J. Wang and B. H. Calhoun, "Techniques to Extend Canary-Based Standby V_{DD} Scaling for SRAMs to 45 nm and Beyond," *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 43, no. 11, pp. 2514–2523, Nov. 2008. doi: 10.1109/JSSC.2008.2005814.
- [56] C. Dray, N. Badereddine, and C. Chanussot, "A 40nm low power SRAM retention circuit with PVT-aware self-refreshing virtual VDD regulation," in *IEEE International Memory Workshop*, (Seoul, South Korea), pp. 46–49, IEEE, May 2010. doi: 10.1109/IMW.2010.5488323.
- [57] L. B. Zordan *et al.*, "A built-in scheme for testing and repairing voltage regulators of low-power SRAMs," in *IEEE 31st VLSI Test Symposium (VTS)*, (Berkeley, California, USA), pp. 77–82, Apr. 2013. doi: 10.1109/VTS.2013.6548894.
- [58] B. S. Lee, "Understanding the Terms and Definitions of LDO Voltage Regulators," Oct. 1999. Texas Instruments application report. Online. Available on <https://www.ti.com/lit/an/slva079/slva079.pdf>.
- [59] R. G. Alía *et al.*, "Heavy Ion Energy Deposition and SEE Intercomparison Within the RADNEXT Irradiation Facility Network," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 70, no. 8, pp. 1596–1605, Aug. 2023. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2023.3260309.